

COMPARATIVE FREQUENCY OF ARRHYTHMIAS IN INFERIOR AND ANTERIOR WALL MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION

Dr. Badar Ahmad Jamal¹, Dr. Ajwa Marrium², Dr. Subyyal Shakil³, Dr. Iqra Ans⁴,
Dr. Nabia Zahid⁵

¹(Post Graduate Resident Cardiology at National Hospital & Medical Center) – corresponding author.

²(Post Graduate Resident Cardiology at National Hospital & Medical Center)

³(Consultant Cardiologist at National Hospital & Medical Center)

⁴(Medical Officer, Dept. of Cardiology – National Hospital & Medical Center)

⁵(Senior House Officer, Royal Blackburn Teaching Hospital, England)

*badarjamal.ajm97@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15781371>

Keywords

Myocardial Infarction,
Arrhythmias, Anterior wall MI,
Inferior wall MI, ST-elevation,
Cardiac monitoring

Article History

Received on 02 June 2025

Accepted on 23 June 2025

Published on 30 June 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Badar Ahmad Jamal

Abstract

This study was aimed to compare the prevalence and the nature of arrhythmias in patients of acute anterior wall ST-elevation myocardial infarction (AWMI) and inferior wall ST-elevation myocardial infarction (IWMI) during their stay in the hospital. It was carried out at National Hospital and Medical Center, Lahore, a tertiary care setup. Adult patients ≥ 15 years of age with ST-elevation MI of either anterior (AWMI) or inferior (IWMI) territory, whereas the exclusion criteria included the presence of preexisting cardiomyopathies, channelopathies, or electrolyte disturbances. The cardiac rhythm was observed continuously via cardiac monitors, arrhythmias if detected, were confirmed and documented with the help of 12-lead ECG. The statistical analysis was performed in SPSS software, version 20. A substantial percentage of patients (70 per cent) revealed to have arrhythmias; the frequency was significantly higher in AWMI (62.9 per cent) than in IWMI cases (37.1 per cent). The most prevalent arrhythmias was premature ventricular contractions PVCs (51.4%) followed by ventricular tachycardia VT (17.1%) being the second most observed arrhythmia. High degree AV block was more common in IWMI (10 percent) and Wenckebach AV block occurred only in IWMI (7.1percent). Additional less commonly arrhythmias included atrial fibrillation (4.3%), and ventricular fibrillation (2.9%). AWMI had more arrhythmias compared to IWMI and PVCs, VT remained the most common ones. AV blocks were more frequent in IWMI. Such results highlight the importance of preemptive monitoring and management plans that should be dependent on the location of infarcts. Upon these observations it is desirable that further large-scale study be conducted.

INTRODUCTION

Ischemic Heart disease, secondary to atherosclerotic coronary artery disease stands globally as a major cause of morbidity and mortality 1. The global burden has been estimated to involve 126 million individuals that is around 1.72% of the world's

population². This gigantic number is still on rise in the modern era which is plagued with health hazards by virtue of unhealthy lifestyle including limited physical activity, excessive consumption of junk food, tobacco smoking, recreational drug abuse,

overwhelming mental stress and so and so forth¹. This isn't the case just with the western world and developed countries but also holds true in our population, here in Indo-Pak subcontinent which is undergoing excessive urbanization and massive adaptation of urban lifestyle full of modifiable risk factors for cardiovascular diseases. Ischemic heart disease is an iceberg of medical ailment with acute coronary syndrome (ACS) counting as the tip of this iceberg being the most life threatening presentation out of the spectrum of cardiac symptoms⁴. Out of which ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) is considered the most dreaded entity with significant morbidity and mortality bearing a number of immediate and delayed complications. Amongst these arrhythmias especially that of ventricular origin are well known to cause hemodynamic compromise and even sudden cardiac death especially in immediate post MI period⁵.

Reportedly around 90% of the patients undergoing acute MI suffer some kind of dysrhythmias during the event or in immediate post MI course and in 25% out of these, arrhythmias happen to occur in first 24 hours⁵. These commonly include atrial fibrillation (AF), paroxysmal supraventricular tachycardia (SVT), accelerated junctional rhythm, atrial/junctional bradycardia, AV blocks, ventricular tachycardia (VT), ventricular fibrillation (VF) etc.⁵ This is said to be in consequence to post MI autonomic dysfunction, enhanced automaticity of myocardium and at times due to confounding electrolyte disturbances⁵. The relative incidence of these rhythm disturbances is higher in STEMI⁵. A study from NICVD Karachi in 2021 reports the prevalence of arrhythmias in patients undergoing primary PCI in 24 hours post PCI span to be 89.1% with accelerated idioventricular rhythm being the most common type of arrhythmia⁴.

Likewise, another study conducted in Combined Military Hospital Kharian, showed that almost all the patients in acute phase of anterior wall MI and inferior wall MI suffered some kind of arrhythmia during in-hospital stay. 56% of study population suffered PVCs, 11 % suffered VT and 9 percent developed second degree AV block with rest of the population having other arrhythmias in comparatively smaller proportion⁶.

A number of studies to date have been done regarding the prevalence of post MI arrhythmias but much hasn't been done in regard of comparative frequency of arrhythmias during the hospital stay in patients with acute anterior wall MI (AWMI) and inferior wall myocardial infarction (IWMI). Same is the subject matter and objective of our study.

Materials and Methods

It was an observational cross sectional study aimed to determine and compare the types of arrhythmias in anterior and inferior wall ST Elevation myocardial infarction. It was carried out at National Hospital & Medical Center, a tertiary-care setup in Lahore. Study population consisted of in-hospital patients admitted with the diagnosis of acute anterior wall myocardial infarction (AWMI) or inferior wall myocardial infarction (IWMI). Inclusion criteria were defined as adult patients (age ≥ 15 years) who had ischemic symptoms and corresponding ECG changes consistent with acute ST elevation MI of either anterior or inferior territory as per standard definition¹⁸. Patients who were known to have any ischemic or non-ischemic cardiomyopathy, hereditary channelopathy, electrolyte imbalance (Na, K, Mg), any previously documented significant arrhythmia (except in the setting of ACS or some other reversible pathology) were excluded from the study. With informed consent, a total of 100 patients who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled for the study from December, 2024 to June, 2025, a period of 6 months.

Data was collected from emergency department, cardiac catheterization lab and Indoor patients qualifying for study. Cardiac electrical rhythm was monitored via cardiac monitors throughout hospital stay. Any arrhythmias if noticed on cardiac monitors, was confirmed and documented by 12-leads ECG except for very short lived arrhythmias such as occasional runs of PVCs that could only be witnessed via cardiac monitor. Type and respective duration of every noticed arrhythmia was documented during the hospital stay.

Data was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Frequency of both types of ST elevation MI (STEMI) along with frequency and types of associated arrhythmias was ascertained for comparison.

Results

A total of 100 patients were included in the study out of which 59 (59%) were males and 41 (41%) were females. Mean age of the participants was 62 years (SD 10.0, range 38-90 years). Out of this population, 53 reported with anterior wall STEMI (AWMI) while 47 were diagnosed with inferior wall STEMI (IWMI). Detailed description of arrhythmias is given in Table 1. 70% of the sample population revealed to have some kind of arrhythmias during the hospital stay, whereas no arrhythmias were observed in remaining 30% patients. Out of these 70%, 44 (62.9%) patients had presented with anterior wall MI and 26 (37.1%) with inferior wall MI. Talking about types of arrhythmias (Table 2), the most frequently encountered arrhythmia was PVCs, which was observed in 36 patients (51.4%) including 28 patients with anterior wall MI and 8 patients with inferior wall MI. This was followed by VT as the second most prevalent arrhythmia. It was observed in

12 patients (17.1%) as a whole including 10 patients with anterior wall MI and two patients with inferior wall MI. Third most frequently observed arrhythmia was high degree AV block including Mobitz II, 2:1 AV block and 3rd degree AV Block. A total of 7 patients including 5 patients with inferior wall MI and 2 with anterior wall developed high degree AV block at some point during the hospital course, representing 10% of total arrhythmias. Next in line was 2ND degree type I AV block (Wenckebach). It was reported in 5 patients, all of whom had inferior wall MI accounting for 7.1% of all the arrhythmias. Other types of arrhythmias were less frequently noted. Those included AF (4.2%), cardiac arrest (4.3%), SVT (2.9%), VF (2.9%). According to our analysis, overall frequency of arrhythmias was significantly higher in patients suffering from anterior wall MI as compared to patients with inferior wall MI

Table 1

Sr	Arrhythmias	Type of MI		Total
		AWMI	IWMI	
1	Yes	44	26	70
2	No	9	21	30
Total		53	47	100

Table 2

Sr.	Type of Arrhythmia	Type of MI		Total, % out of arrhythmias	% out of study population
		AWMI	IWMI		
1	PVCs	28 (40%)	8 (11.4%)	36 (51.4%)	36%
2	VT	10 (14.3)	2 (2.8%)	12 (17.1%)	12%
3	AF	1 (1.4%)	2 (2.8%)	3 (4.3%)	3%
4	Wenckebach AV Block	0	5 (7.1%)	5 (7.1%)	5%
5	High Degree AV block	2 (2.8%)	5 (7.1%)	7 (10%)	7%
6	SVT	0	2 (2.8%)	2 (2.8%)	2%
7	VF	2 (2.8%)	0	2 (2.8%)	2%
8	Cardiac arrest / Asystole	1 (1.4%)	2 (2.8%)	3 (4.3%)	3%
TOTAL		44(62.9%)	26 (37.1%)	70 (100%)	70%

Discussion

Our study population comprised patients diagnosed with either AWMI or IWMI among whom 70% were reported to have some kind of arrhythmia during hospitalization. Now if we compare the frequency of

arrhythmias in both types of MI, our data indicate that arrhythmias were far more prevalent in AWMI as compared to IWMI. This is consistent with data reported by Siddique M.B. et al and Nagabhushana S et al. both of whom have shown the arrhythmias to

be more prevalent in anterior wall MI as compared to inferior wall MI^{6, 7}. This point is particularly noteworthy considering the fact that SA node and AV node – crucial components in cardiac electrical impulse generation and transition – both are primarily supplied by RCA (and less commonly by LCx) which is typically involved in IWMI, still arrhythmias are more prevalent in AAMI patients^{8,9}. In our understanding, this apparent contradiction can be attributed to the fact that PVCs – the most frequently observed arrhythmia – were reported in vast majority of patients diagnosed with AAMI. Although PVCs occurred in IWMI patients as well, they were less frequent in this group as compared to those with IWMI. Conversely, bradyarrhythmias including atrioventricular blocks and cardiac arrest were found to be more prevalent in patients suffering from inferior wall MI. The incidence of bradyarrhythmias in the setting of ACS has been reported to be up to 18% in literature¹¹. According to stat pearls, 9% of the patients with inferior wall MI develop AV blocks mostly in first 24 hours of acute MI¹¹. Likewise another study published in Pak Armed Forces Medical Journal in April 2016 indicated this percentage to be 28%¹². Our data revealed that 12% patients developed some kind of AV block predominantly occurring in those with inferior wall MI.

Ventricular tachycardia (VT) is another dreadful arrhythmia that is frequently observed in patients with acute MI and its occurrence significantly impacts overall risk of mortality¹³. Data of some 5000 patients from SPACE registry Saudi Arabia revealed the frequency of ventricular arrhythmias (including ventricular tachycardia and ventricular fibrillation) in the setting of ACS to be 3.3%¹⁴. In another research study carried out in Peshawar Pakistan, demonstrated that ventricular tachycardia occurred in 7% of the patients admitted with acute coronary syndrome (ACS)¹⁵. In the similar fashion, our study identified VT as the second most frequently encountered arrhythmia in the setting of ST elevation myocardial infarction. However it is noteworthy that majority of the available data reporting the incidence and prevalence of VT in the setting of ACS doesn't clearly distinguish between ST elevation M (STEMI)I and non-ST elevation MI (NSTEMI). In contrast, our study estimated its

frequency exclusively in patients with ST elevation MI (AAMI, IWMI) providing unique insight in this context.

Another interesting fact that we found in our study was co-existence of supraventricular tachycardia (SVT) with acute STEMI, the thing which according to literature is fairly uncommon and limited to case reports, with true prevalence being unknown¹⁶. In our study, SVT was documented in two patients during the hospital course, both of whom were diagnosed with inferior wall MI.

Conclusion

Acute ST elevation MI of both anterior and inferior territory is frequently complicated by development of arrhythmias, many of which pose a substantial risk in terms of morbidity and mortality. The current study demonstrates that arrhythmias are more prevalent in anterior wall ST-elevation MI (AAMI) as compared to inferior wall ST-elevation MI (IWMI). Furthermore, our data identify premature ventricular complexes (PVCs) as the most frequently occurring arrhythmia, followed by ventricular tachycardia (VT), atrial fibrillation (AF) and high degree AV blocks. Other arrhythmias including supraventricular tachycardia (SVT), Wenkebach AV block, ventricular fibrillation (VF), asystole / cardiac arrest were reported to be less common. Comparative data on frequency of arrhythmias in aforementioned types of MI remains limited, highlighting the need for large-scale observational studies are needed.

References

1. World Health Organization. Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs). Fact sheet, updated 11 June 2021. Available from: [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-\(cvds\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cardiovascular-diseases-(cvds))
2. Khan MA, Hashim MJ, Mustafa H, Baniyas MY, Al Suwaidi SKBM, AlKatheeri R, et al. Global epidemiology of ischemic heart disease: Results from the global burden of disease study [Internet]. Cureus. U.S. National Library of Medicine; 2020 [cited 2023May3]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7384703/>

3. Jafar TH, Qadri Z, Chaturvedi N. Coronary artery disease epidemic in Pakistan: More electrocardiographic evidence of ischaemia in women than in men [Internet]. Heart (British Cardiac Society). U.S. National Library of Medicine; 2008 [cited 2023May3]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2565583/>
4. Shah JA, Naz F, Kumar R, Hassan M, Shah G, Ahmed K, et al. Incidence of cardiac arrhythmias in acute myocardial infarction patients undergoing primary percutaneous coronary intervention and associated outcomes during the first 24 Hours [Internet]. Cureus. U.S. National Library of Medicine; 2021 [cited 2023May3]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7871363/>
5. Harsha S Nagarajarao MD. Complications of myocardial infarction [Internet]. Overview, Arrhythmic Complications of MI, Arrhythmic Complications: Supraventricular Tachyarrhythmias. Medscape; 2022 [cited 2023May3]. Available from: <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/164924-overview#a2>
6. Siddique MB et al. Frequencies and patterns of arrhythmias in anterior and inferior myocardial infarction. *Pak Armed Forces Med J* 2009; 59(4):450-4
7. S N, GK R kumar, Ranganatha M, Virupakshappa V. Study of arrhythmias in acute myocardial infarction [Internet]. [cited 2025 Jun 24]. Available from: <https://ijmrr.medresearch.in/index.php/ijmrr/article/view/303>
8. Nordick K, Tedder BL, Zemaitis MR. Anatomy, Thorax, Sinoatrial Nodal Artery. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. [Updated 2023 Dec 9; cited 2025 Jun 24]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK541008/>
9. Pejković B, Krajnc I, Anderhuber F, Kosutić D. Anatomical aspects of the arterial blood supply to the sinoatrial and atrioventricular nodes of the human heart. *J Int Med Res*. 2008 Jul-Aug;36(4):691-698. doi:10.1177/147323000803600410
10. Trappe HJ. Tachyarrhythmias, bradyarrhythmias and acute coronary syndromes. *J Emerg Trauma Shock*. 2010 Apr-Jun;3(2):137-142. doi:10.4103/0974-2700.62112
11. Warner MJ, Tivakaran VS. Inferior myocardial infarction. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025 Jan-. [Updated 2023 Feb 12; cited 2025 Jun 24]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470572/>
12. Mehreen S, Ahmed A, Tahir M. Frequency of high-degree AV blocks in acute inferior myocardial infarction and their impact on clinical outcomes. *Pak Armed Forces Med J*. 2016 Apr 30;66(2):281-4.
13. Piccini JP, White JA, Mehta RH, Lokhnygina Y, Al-Khatib SM, Tricoci P, et al. Sustained ventricular tachycardia and ventricular fibrillation complicating non-ST-segment-elevation acute coronary syndromes. *Circulation*. 2012 Jul 3;126(1):41-9. doi: 10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.111.071860
14. Hersi AS, Alhabib KF, AlFaleh H, Al Nemer K, Al Saif S, Taraben A, et al. Incidence of ventricular arrhythmia and associated patient outcomes in hospitalized acute coronary syndrome patients in Saudi Arabia: findings from the registry of the Saudi Project for Assessment of Acute Coronary Syndrome (SPACE). *Ann Saudi Med*. 2012 Jul-Aug;32(4):372-7. doi:10.5144/0256-4947.2012.372
15. Kamal A, Faheem M. Frequency of ventricular tachycardia in patients with acute coronary syndrome during the first 24 hours of admission. *J Med Sci*. 2024 Jul-Sep;32(3):250-254. doi:10.52764/jms.24.32.3.8

16. Bhardwaj, S., Narla, S., Absur, M. N., Dutta, S., Hyzil, J. B., & Ganesh, S. K. (2025, February). Augmented Reality-Assisted Pediatric Surgery: A Machine Learning-Based Approach for Enhancing Accuracy. In *2025 First International Conference on Advances in Computer Science, Electrical, Electronics, and Communication Technologies (CE2CT)* (pp. 832-836). IEEE.
17. Subramanian A, Lysander A. Unusual presentation of acute myocardial infarction. *Indian Pacing Electrophysiol J.* 2012 Sep;12(5):233. doi:10.1016/S0972-6292(16)30547-2.
18. Wagner GS, Macfarlane P, Wellens H, Josephson M, Gorgels A, Mirvis DM, Pahlm O, Surawicz B, Kligfield P, Childers R, Gettes LS, Bailey JJ, Deal BJ, Hancock EW, Kors JA, Mason JW, Okin P, Rautaharju PM, van Herpen G; American Heart Association Electrocardiography and Arrhythmias Committee; ACCF; HRS. AHA/ACCF/HRS recommendations for the standardization and interpretation of the electrocardiogram: part VI: acute ischemia/infarction. *Circulation.* 2009 Mar 17;119(10):e262-70. doi:10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.108.19109
19. IMPROVEMENTS IN AI-POWERED REMOTE PATIENT MONITORING FOR HEART PATIENTS AND AI-POWERED INDIVIDUALIZED TREATMENT PLANS. (2025). *The Research of Medical Science Review*, 3(3), 744-763. <https://thermsr.com/index.php/Journal/article/view/813>